

Evaluation of Final Outcomes after High Tibial Osteotomies in the Treatment of Osteoarthritis**Battu Maheswara Reddy¹, Nagesh Muddamsetti², Y G Raghava Naidu³, Saya Venkateswara Prasad⁴**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Orthopedics, Department of Orthopedics, Viswabharathi Medical College and General Hospital, Penchikalapadu, Kurnool, Andhra Pradesh²Assistant Professor, Department of Orthopedics, Department of Orthopedics, Viswabharathi Medical College and General Hospital, Penchikalapadu, Kurnool, Andhra Pradesh³Assistant Professor, Department of Orthopedics, Department of Orthopedics, Viswabharathi Medical College and General Hospital, Penchikalapadu, Kurnool, Andhra Pradesh⁴Associate Professor, Department of Orthopedics, Viswabharathi Medical College and General Hospital, Penchikalapadu, Kurnool, Andhra Pradesh

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Abstract:

Background: High tibial osteotomy (HTO) and uni-compartmental knee arthroplasty are both treatment options for isolated uni-compartmental osteoarthritis (OA) of the knee and Knee joint instability. Before the advent of knee arthroplasties, HTO was the most commonly performed surgical procedure for knee OA. HTO is a well-established procedure used to treat uni-compartmental conditions like overload or osteoarthritis by shifting the mechanical axis of the knee, thereby realigning the load distribution. This realignment can help reduce pain, improve function, and potentially slow the progression of osteoarthritis.

Aim of the Study: To analyse the final outcome of the High Osteotomy in Osteoarthritis patients after a follow up of 2 years.

Materials: 29 consecutive patients with Osteoarthritis patients attending the Department of Orthopedics, from May 2022 to August 2024 were included in a prospective case series study. All the patients were graded according to Kellgren Lawrence classification with radiological evidence of Osteoarthritis with valgus and/or varus deformities and medial compartmental osteoarthritis (OA). Patients aged between 45 years and 65 years were included. Patients with high-demand activity levels without running or jumping were included. Patients with varus mal-alignment less than 15° were included. Patients with metaphyseal varus of the tibia greater than 5° were included. Patients with full range of motion and normal lateral and patella-femoral compartments were included. Deformity analysis was based on full-leg weight-bearing radiographs, either digitally or on paper. Arthroscopy was done initially to assess the status of the cartilage and menisci, especially in the lateral compartment. Wherever necessary, medial meniscus was resected, smoothing of the cartilage done and ablation of osteophytes were done to address any extension deficits. All the patients were followed up for 2 years.

Results: 29 patients were treated with HTO, with an average age of 45.62±5.35 years. The average osteotomy opening was 10.8 mm, and no cases of secondary loss of correction occurred. One patient required a reoperation shortly after the initial procedure due to overcorrection, which was corrected by removing distal locking screws, adjusting the leg axis, and securing the plate with bi-cortical locking screws. Two patients experienced late infection and soft-tissue irritation 4 months postoperatively, but after plate removal and antibiotic treatment, the further clinical course was complication-free.

Conclusions: Realignment osteotomy remains a critical treatment option for early to medium-grade varus medial compartment osteoarthritis (OA). Open-wedge high tibial osteotomy (HTO) utilizing optimal surgical techniques (including bi-planar metaphyseal osteotomy) and fixation with the TomoFix internal plate fixator has proven to be effective in treating uni-compartmental gonarthrosis, even in the absence of bone grafts or substitutes. The complication rate is low, patients achieve full weight-bearing quickly, and the medium-term results are promising.

Keywords: Osteoarthritis, High Tibial Osteotomy, Instability of Knee, alignment and varus deformity.

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Introduction

Knee osteoarthritis (OA) is more prevalent in women and older individuals. [1] In addition to aging, significant evidence, primarily from North American and European cohorts, suggests that obesity and strenuous occupational physical activities are key risk factors for symptomatic knee OA. [2] A systematic review found that the factors most consistently associated with knee OA include obesity, previous knee trauma, hand OA, female sex, and older age. In young adults, knee OA is predominantly the result of a previous knee injury. [3] High tibial osteotomies (HTO) and uni-compartmental knee arthroplasties are commonly performed to treat isolated uni-compartmental knee OA. [4] Before the advent of knee arthroplasties, HTO was the most common surgical treatment for knee OA.

Over the last two decades, the incidence of osteotomies has decreased, but symptomatic knee OA with mild to moderate radiological signs is still frequently seen as an indication for HTO in young, active patients. [5] HTO results are generally favorable, though they tend to worsen over time, with many patients eventually requiring total knee arthroplasty (TKA). [6] However, most of the existing reports on HTO outcomes come from single-center or single-surgeon studies which limits the generalizing their findings. There is a lack of larger, registry-based studies reporting on HTO results in broader practice. [7] HTO changes the anatomy and biomechanics of the knee, with the most common alterations including ligamentous imbalance, patellar tendon length changes, scar tissue formation, and potential rotational deformities. [8]

These factors can complicate subsequent TKA, but the majority of previous studies show no significant negative effects on TKA outcomes. However, these studies often involve small cohort sizes, with only one registry-based study revealing that TKA after an osteotomy has nearly three times the early revision rate compared to a primary TKA. [9] HTO is considered a viable alternative for isolated medial compartment knee OA, offering the benefits of pain relief, functional maintenance, and delayed TKA, particularly in patients whose articular cartilage has not yet completely worn away and in younger individuals who wish to maintain their activity levels. [10] With the growing popularity of TKA, the role of HTO in treating knee OA has diminished since its introduction by Jackson in 1958.

However, in the 1990s, the role of correcting varus alignment in treating ligamentous injuries and knee imbalances led to a renewed interest in osteotomy in sports medicine. [11] The Kellgren–Lawrence classification is the most commonly used radiological staging for OA, with the Ahlbäck classification also being frequently employed. [12] A major

drawback of radiological classifications is that they only assess the radiological severity of OA and do not provide information about symptoms or functional outcomes. [13] Their utility in determining treatment strategies is limited, as these classifications are observer-dependent and tend to have poor reproducibility, making them prone to bias. In the present study the final outcomes of the HTO in Osteoarthritis patients was analysed. Fujisawa et al. [14] demonstrated that the best outcomes from valgization displacement osteotomy are achieved when the postoperative mechanical axis intersects the joint line at approximately 62% of the medial/lateral width of the tibial head, a finding confirmed by Agneskirchner et al. [15] through biomechanical experiments. The 62% point, located slightly lateral to the intercondylar eminence, was marked on the knee baseline during planning.

Materials

The present study was conducted among the 29 Osteoarthritis patients attending the Department of Orthopedics, from May 2022 to August 2024. A prospective case series study was conducted at Viswabharathi Medical College and General Hospital, Kurnool. The study was approved by the institutional ethics committee in the Orthopedic Department of the Hospital. A total of 29 patients with radiological evidence of Osteoarthritis with valgus and/or varus deformities and medial compartmental osteoarthritis (OA) were included.

Inclusion criteria: Patients aged between 45 years and 65 years were included. Patients of both the genders were included. Patients willing to participate in the study were included. Patients falling in the categories as defined by the International Society of Arthroscopy, Knee Surgery, and orthopedic Sports Medicine were included. Patients with isolated medial joint line pain, with BMI less than 30 were included. Patients with high-demand activity levels without running or jumping were included. Patients with varus mal-alignment less than 15° were included. Patients with metaphyseal varus of the tibia greater than 5° were included. Patients with full range of motion and normal lateral and patella-femoral compartments were included.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients less than 45 years and more than 65 years were excluded. Patients with defect in the postero-medial tibia were excluded. Patients with abnormal ligament balance, smoking status, and a certain level of pain tolerance were excluded. All patients meeting the inclusion criteria underwent high tibial osteotomy (HTO). The most ideal candidates for HTO for medial knee OA, as the potential to return to sports activity was also considered a significant factor in the treatment decision-making process.

Preoperative planning: It involved deformity analysis based on full-leg weight-bearing radiographs, either digitally or on paper. The magnification factor of the radiograph was considered, and the required osteotomy opening was measured on the medial tibial cortex. Surgical procedures were carried out with the patient in a supine position on the operating table, using a knee bench and a foot-rest. The leg, including the iliac crest, was draped free for possible bone-graft harvesting and to enable intra-operative monitoring of the leg's axis. The surgery was performed with the knee flexed at 45° and the foot resting on the operating table, and tourniquets were generally not needed. The image intensifier was positioned on the opposite side of the table to monitor the surgery.

Operative Technique adopted: Arthroscopy was done initially to assess the status of the cartilage and menisci, especially in the lateral compartment. Wherever necessary, medial meniscus was resected, smoothing of the cartilage done and ablation of osteophytes were done to address any extension deficits. The surgical approach took into account pre-existing scars, with a 6-8 cm incision made from the insertion of the pes anserinus to the postero-medial corner of the tibial head, although longitudinal incisions were also an option.

The tendons of the pes anserinus were retracted, and the distal fibers of the superficial medial collateral ligament were carefully detached to expose the tibial rear edge. Using image intensifier monitoring, two 3.0-mm Lancet tipped K-wires were placed to mark the height and direction of the horizontal osteotomy. The K-wire in the antero-posterior plane marked the joint center and was placed parallel to the tibial slope, targeting the proximal tibio-fibular joint. The wires were positioned to end at the lateral tibial cortex. The depth of the osteotomy was measured, subtracting 10 mm from the total depth of transection as assessed by the image intensifier.

The osteotomy procedure:

It began with a horizontal cut below the guiding wires in the posterior two-thirds of the tibia. An anterior ascending osteotomy in the ventral third of the tibia ran upward, cranially, behind the tuberosity, and through the far cortex, forming an angle of approximately 110°. The oscillating saw was continuously flushed during the procedure. Once the desired osteotomy depth was reached, flat chisels were inserted into the horizontal gap, slowly opening it to the predetermined width before being replaced with a bone spreader.

After correcting the leg axis, clinical and radiological assessments were made, paying particular attention to the tibial slope in the sagittal plane. The osteotomy gap opening was adjusted based on the specific deformity, with greater opening posteriorly

for pure varus correction and more anteriorly in cases of extension deficit or anterior knee instability. The internal plate fixator, with eight unidirectional conical and combi-holes, was inserted, and screws were placed under image-intensifier control. The distal locking screw was used temporarily to compress the lateral cortex bridge, followed by the insertion of locking screws from distal to proximal.

The lag screw was replaced with a bi-cortical locking screw, and the bone spreader was removed. Autologous bone grafts were avoided when the bone contact was good, but bone substitutes were used for larger gaps, especially in osteoporotic bone. Postoperatively, patients began mobilizing on day 1 with forearm crutches and partial weight-bearing, with gradual increase depending on pain levels.

Full weight-bearing without crutches was generally possible by the fifth postoperative week, and normal weight-bearing was expected by the sixth week. No restrictions were placed on knee joint range of motion, and orthodesis was not necessary. Antithrombotic prophylaxis with low-molecular-weight heparin was continued until full weight-bearing was achieved.

Post-operative management: Radiographic examinations were performed on the third postoperative day and again at 6 weeks, with a full-leg weight-bearing radiograph taken at a later date. Bone healing in the lateral and anterior bone bridges was confirmed by these examinations, and it was emphasized that full weight-bearing and physical activity could resume even before complete bone remodeling, which may take up to a year. Implant removal was considered after 12–18 months if necessary, with approximately 20% of patients in this study undergoing implant removal.

Results

In this study which was planned in a prospective method was conducted on 29 Osteoarthritis patients. Radiological outcomes for open-wedge osteotomy without filling material have been debated, with some surgeons favoring the use of filling materials or substances to promote bone formation in the gap.

In this prospective case series of 15 (51.72%) patients, ossification of the gap progressed from the lateral hinge to the medial side, with bone healing starting at the osteotomy surfaces and closing within 6–18 months. Implant removal was not recommended before 12 months. A randomized clinical trial comparing fixation stability between open-wedge HTO with T-plate and closed-wedge procedures found both methods provided excellent initial stability and maintained correction for up to 2 years.

In the clinical part of this study, 29 patients were treated with HTO, with an average age of 45.62 ± 5.35 years. The average osteotomy opening was 10.8 mm, and no cases of secondary loss of correction occurred. One patient required a re-operation shortly after the initial procedure due to overcorrection, which was corrected by removing

distal locking screws, adjusting the leg axis, and securing the plate with bi-cortical locking screws. Two patients experienced late infection and soft-tissue irritation 4 months postoperatively, but after plate removal and antibiotic treatment, the further clinical course was complication-free.

Table 1: Kellgren Lawrence [12] classification adopted for grading Osteoarthritis in the study

Grades	Radiological signs	Number, (%)
I	Doubtful narrowing of the joint space, possible osteophytes	0
II	Small osteophytes, possible narrowing of the joint	0
III	Multiple, moderately sized osteophytes, definite joint space narrowing, some sclerotic areas, possible deformation of bone ends	08 (27.58%)
IV	Multiple large osteophytes, severe joint space narrowing, marked sclerosis and definite deformity of bone ends.	21 (72.41%)

Discussion:

In this study which was planned in a prospective method was conducted on 29 Osteoarthritis patients. Radiological outcomes for open-wedge osteotomy without filling material have been debated, with some surgeons favoring the use of filling materials or substances to promote bone formation in the gap. In this prospective case series of 15 (51.72%) patients, ossification of the gap progressed from the lateral hinge to the medial side, with bone healing starting at the osteotomy surfaces and closing within 6–18 months. Implant removal was not recommended before 12 months. In collaboration with the AO-CID (AO Foundation, Davos), a multicenter retrospective outcome analysis was conducted on 538 patients who underwent valgization tibial osteotomy between 2004 and 2006 (publication 2010). The Oxford Knee Score, [16] a key evaluation tool for both knee uni-condylar prosthesis and total knee replacement, was the primary criterion used in this study. This score, which appears frequently in international publications, consists of 12 questions answered by the patient on a five-point scale, allowing for a score range from 0 to 48 points. The average follow-up period was 3.6 years (ranging from 2.4 to 4.7 years), with an average BMI of 27 and an average osteotomy opening of 10 mm. On average, patients achieved an Oxford score of 40, with no significant differences observed across age groups. Even in the 60-year-old patient group, very good medium-term outcomes were achieved when the indications were appropriate. [17] Postoperative complications included one implant breakage, eight cases of insufficient bone healing (which were diagnosed early and treated with reoperation), 11 hematomas, 11 infections, three infected hematomas, and two instances of impaired wound healing. The AO-KNEG 2009 recommendations [18] for cases of delayed bone healing suggest the use of cancellous bone from the iliac crest for large gaps or slow bone healing. In cases of delayed union, a computed tomographic

scan and the application of cancellous bone in a second surgery are recommended. No cases required lateral secondary osteosynthesis. When compared to published outcomes for prostheses, the functional results of this procedure were found to be highly favorable, with a low complication rate, supporting the recommendation for this procedure. In a study by Noyes et al., [19] the authors found no significant differences in symptoms such as pain, swelling, and giving way between patients treated with high tibial osteotomy (HTO) alone, HTO combined with a Losee-type extra-articular procedure, or HTO combined with ACL reconstruction. Loures FB, Correia W et al., [20] however, reported higher complication rates when HTO was performed simultaneously with ACL reconstruction, compared to either HTO alone or a staged approach. No other studies included in this review found a high complication rate with combined HTO and ACL reconstruction procedures. Other studies [21,22] suggested that HTO can be safely performed alongside ACL reconstruction. A recent systematic review by Li et al. [23] found that young patients with medial compartment osteoarthritis and ACL deficiency experienced improvements in subjective scores, and most returned to recreational sports after undergoing both HTO and ACL reconstruction simultaneously.

Conclusions

Realignment osteotomy remains a critical treatment option for early to medium-grade varus medial compartment osteoarthritis (OA). Open-wedge high tibial osteotomy (HTO) utilizing optimal surgical techniques (including bi-planar metaphyseal osteotomy) and fixation with the TomoFix internal plate fixator has proven to be effective in treating uni-compartmental gonarthrosis, even in the absence of bone grafts or substitutes. The complication rate is low, patients achieve full weight-bearing quickly, and the medium-term results are promising.

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